

EFFECT OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON EMPLOYEES' SATISFACTION, ENGAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Employees have felt more safe and driven as a result of transformational leadership. As a result, their engagement and performance improve. This research aims to develop a conceptual framework for evaluating the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction, with employee engagement and performance serving as a mediating variable . Survey data collected from 246 employees from financial institutions in Mumbai. Results from the multiple regression analysis using SPSS version 22 indicated that the influence of transformational leadership on job satisfaction, employee engagement, and performance is enormous.

Key words: Transformational Leadership, employee engagement, Regression Analysis

INTRODUCTION

The role of leaders in directing and managing employees to achieve the company's goals is critical in order to improve employee performance. Without a leader, the organisation is simply a collection of employees working together without any direction to achieve the company's objectives (Da-nim, 2004). Leaders are those who can set an example, motivate, enable others to act, and challenge the process for the company's benefit (Bateman & Snell, 2007). As a result, leaders and followers will have to collaborate in order to fulfil the company's objectives. The quality of a company's leader is usually the most important aspect in determining its success or failure (Bass, 1990).

Great leaders need to be able to demonstrate strong moral and ethical standards. They not just to live up to their own standards, but they also have their subordinates' best interests at heart. This type of leader is referred to as a transformational leader (Rothfelder, Ottenbacher, & Harrington, 2012). Transformational leaders offer a positive and appealing vision of the future, are aware of their followers' needs and desires, inspire followers' innovation, and foster team spirit. When followers' needs are met, they are more engaged and satisfied, which may result in their best

performance. The goal of implementing transformational leadership is to increase employee satisfaction and engagement. It was done to better understand employee needs and wants on an individual basis so that senior management may tailor their approach to each person.

The former leader was likewise recognised for not being very professional because he couldn't get along with the personnel. Recent leaders, on the other hand, are capable of making people feel safe and effectively motivating them. Employees are satisfied because the boss respects and cherishes their thoughts and opinions in addition to treating them nicely. As a result, they are more eager to put in extra effort and give it their all. The researchers wish to see if transformational leadership has had an impact on employee performance, using engagement and job satisfaction as a mediating variable.

OBJECTIVE

To provide a conceptual framework for evaluating the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership, according to Gillet.al. (2010), is a method of regulating the conduct and attitude of personnel, in addition to enhancing staff engagement to the company's vision and mission statements, in trying to attain the corporate aim. In addition, transformational leadership relates to the form of leadership which encourage people to evolve in order to attain their full potential. (Yukl, 2010). As a nutshell, transformational leader can be described as a management style that encourages individuals to learn and get better their productivity. Transformational leadership has the potential to help employees function effectively for the benefit of the organisation. All of this inspires management and staff to work together to accomplish the corporate goal.

Job Satisfaction

Employees will be satisfied because they are appreciated individually if leaders can recognise their distinctions and appreciate them appropriately in accomplishing their responsibilities. Every employee is satisfied to a different degree. Job satisfaction, according to Judge et al. (2012), is a complex psychological response to individual employment.

Job satisfaction refers to the happy sensations that employees can experience as a result of their jobs' important values and significance to them (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, & Patrick, 2006). As a result, job satisfaction can be defined as an individual's reaction to his or her work environment. Employees may be more content in their occupations if they find more suitable characteristics in their work environments.

It is obvious that each employee's level of happiness varies depending on the values he or she holds. The more suitable components of his or her employment he or she may identify, the more committed he or she will be. Employees that are committed to the organisation feel tied to it and become a part of it, thus they are more likely to do a better job.

Employee Performance

Employee performance refers to a person's capacity to complete duties based on qualifications, knowledge, flexibility, and honesty (Hasibuan, 2005). As per Mangkune gara (2005), employee performance is the consequence of a staff's theoretical and practical efforts in performing out his or her obligations in connection with the duty assigned to him or her. That's to do with whether personnels work hard to complete their duties they've been given.

Employee performance is defined as an employee's results at the end relation to the work assigned by the company. Whenever people who perform effectively, it seems to have a positive influence on the organization's effectiveness.

Employee engagement

Employee engagement is concerned with problems such as loyalty, fulfillment, and organizational behavior, according to Saks, A.M. (2006). Personal involvement, according to W.A. Kahn (1990), is where During work roles, individuals use it and exhibit themselves in physiological, intellectual, and psychological ways by holding their respective definitions and interpretations of participation and detachment. Engagement is defined by its energy, involvement, and efficacy, which contrasts dramatically with the three meltdown characteristics of tiredness, cynicism, and inefficacy (Maslach, C et.al. 2001).

In these difficult times, employee engagement is considered as a major source of competitive advantage. Employees are the primary assets of every firm, according to Bedarkar & Pandita (2014), The individuals will become alienated when they're not given the appropriate time and place to develop a flawless balance between work and personal and fun at workplace. To fulfil their aims and objectives, both the enterprise and the personnel rely on each other. As a corollary, employee participation should not have been viewed as a yet another event, except as an integral component of the company values. Participation of employees should really be a haven't ever loop of learning, progress, and engagement.

Employee engagement encourages workers to put their hearts and souls into their jobs even while providing a feeling of personal. Employee involvement has been linked to increased wellbeing and feelings regarding job and the company, thus according study. Workers don't simply work for a paycheck or an advancement in position; they want to see the company succeed.

Employee Satisfaction and Engagement

By many theorists' apparent endorsement of this link, we can clearly discern a close association between employee pleasure and engagement. Job satisfaction is a critical component of employee engagement, according to (Maylett and Riboldi, 2008), however Garg and Kumar (2012) emphasise the importance of work satisfaction as a crucial driver of engagement. Job satisfaction is a significant driver of employee engagement in a firm, according to their results.

As a corollary, today's businesses must proactively endeavour to fulfill expectations of employees and, as a direct consequence, get an influence on employee performance, which then in turn has a substantial effect on the company's performance.

Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction

According to Tondok & Andarika (2004), among the most crucial factors affecting job happiness is leadership style. Furthermore, dissatisfaction with working conditions is the primary driver of employee turnover. People are unable to engage in judgement call because leadership do not allow them to. Leadership lack objectivity and are unavailable to their minions.

A visionary leadership who brings a notion to life . It persuades people to prioritise the collective's concerns over their own. Transformational leadership is the term used to describe it (Bateman & Snell, 2007). This is also what transpires whenever one or more individuals connect with each other in such a manner that leadership and team members acquire higher degrees of morale and productivity. They work together to meet each other's demands in their different workstations.

According to Farrell et al. (2005), transformational leaders can boost their employees' capacities by devoting attention to the personal aspirations. As a result, transformational leadership seems to be the most effective leadership style for 21st-century organisations. Furthermore, according to Al-Swidi et al. (2012), transformational leadership has been shown to have a significant impact on job satisfaction through increasing employee empowerment. Effective transformational leaders will strive to increase employee demands and pay attention to them. As a result, the employees will be motivated to perform better, resulting in their pleasure. Job satisfaction and organisational commitment are significantly impacted by transformational leaders. (Yang, 2012)

H1: Job satisfaction is positively impacted by transformational leadership.

Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Employee performance can be inclined by job happiness. Personnel that are content in their jobs and committed to their companies are often more prolific. According to Luthans (2006), job happiness and employee performance have a close link. There are distinctions between contented and unsatisfied employees. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to show

up for work and follow company rules, but they are less likely to join labour unions. Employees who are content with their work usually perform better than those who are unsatisfied with their jobs (Handoko, 2009).

Employees that are happy with their work are more likely to act favourably, help others, and go above and beyond the company's expectations. As a result, organisations with contented employees are more productive than companies with disgruntled employees (Robbins & Judge, 2008). Employees who are happy are more likely to do and do their duties well.

H2: Employee performance is positively influenced by job satisfaction.

Transformational Leadership and Employee Performance

Employees will feel confident, trusted, and loyal to transformational leaders because They're also motivated to give it their all, which is often more than they bargained for (Yukl, 2010). To put it another way, transformational leadership has the potential to improve employee performance.

Employee performance will improve when more transformational leadership is used. It also works the other way around: the poorer the transformative leadership, the poorer the staff performance. Transformational leaders are capable of motivating their staff to execute their duties on an individual basis. As a result, it will have a positive impact on employees' contributions to the company (Imran & Anis-ul-Haque, 2011).

Participatory management methods, such as open communication and a participatory leadership style, have also been linked to better levels of satisfaction in studies. Employees are content and respected because their ideas and ingenuity are valued. Indeed, such methods may help employees perform better (Biswas, 2012).

H3: With job satisfaction as a mediating variable, transformational leadership has a favourable and considerable impact on employee performance.

Transformational Leadership and Employee Engagement

Customers' trust and dedication are positively influenced by salespeople's actions. Customer interactions are influenced by transformational leadership behaviour, according to this study. The findings underscored the importance of adapting leadership development in order to encourage and improve sales representatives' abilities. According to Bushra et al. (2011), transformational leadership increases job satisfaction and organisational commitment. To get more satisfied and devoted employees, management should adopt this leadership style. Riaz et al. (2011) discovered a strong and positive link between transformative leadership and affective commitment among employees.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

According to the study's literature, transformational leaders have a beneficial impact on personnel performance. Many researchers have discovered that the characteristics of these leaders have a substantial impact on employee performance. As a result, the current research has developed the framework depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework transformational leaders with personnel performance

CONCLUSION

Hundreds of researches have been conducted to determine how leadership style affects employee performance. In general, this paper looked at a variety of literature studies on transformational leadership in order to develop a conceptual framework for evaluating its impact on employee performance utilising employee engagement and job satisfaction as a mediating variable. As a result, the conceptual framework must be tested using employees as the unit of analysis. In addition, ongoing study will provide us a better knowledge of how leadership style affects employee performance. Professionals who want to improve the crucial people side of their business in a highly competitive setting can benefit from better understanding the relationship between leadership style and employee performance.

REFERENCES

Bedarkar, M & Pandita, D (2014). 'A study on the drivers of employee engagement impacting employee performance'. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 133 (2014) 106 – 115)

- Bushra, F., Usman, A., & Naveed, A. (2011). Effect of transformational leadership on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment in banking sector of Lahore (Pakistan). *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(18), 261-267. Retrieved from: http://www.ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_2_No_18_October_2011/31.pdf
- Garg, A. & Kumar, V. (2012), "A study of employee engagement in pharmaceutical sector", *International Journal of Research in IT and Management*, 2(5), pp. 85-98
- Katz, D. and Kahn, R. L. (1978). *The Social Psychology of Organizations*, (2nd Edition), New York: Wiley
- Maslach, C., Schaufelli, W.B. and Leiter, M.P. (2001), "Job burnout", *Annual Review of Psychology*, Vol. 52, pp. 397-422
- Maylett, T. M. & Riboldi, J. M. (2008), *The Three Essential Components of Employee Engagement*. DecisionWise Inc [Online] Available on: http://www.comphealth.com/sites/comphealth/client-resources/whitepapers/Documents/The_Three_Essential_Components_of_Employee_Engagement.pdf
- Riaz, T., Akram, M., & Ijaz, H. (2011). Impact of transformational leadership style on affective employees' commitment: An empirical study of banking sector in Islamabad (Pakistan). *The Journal of Commerce*, 3(1), 43-51. ISSN: 2220-6043
- Robertson-Smith, G. and Markwick, C (2009), *Employee Engagement: A Review of Current Thinking*. Institute for Employment Studies
- Saks, A.M. (2006). Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement, *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 21(7), 600-19